

Participation and Commitment of Supreme Pupil Government Officers

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Abstract:

The participation and commitment of Supreme Pupil Government (SPG) officers are crucial for the student government's effective functioning and the student body's overall welfare. Along this line of thinking, this study aimed to determine the level of participation and commitment of Supreme Pupil Government Officers to school programs, projects, and activities in a first-class, highly urbanized city in the region of Western Visayas, Philippines, during the School Year 2022-2023. Data for this descriptive study was collected from 100 SPG officers using a 45-item self-made survey questionnaire that has passed the rigorous validity and reliability tests. The results of the study showed that the level of participation and commitment of the Supreme Pupil Government Officers to programs, projects, and activities were very high. No significant difference was found in the level of participation of Supreme Pupil Government Officers when grouped and compared according to sex and grade level in the school programs, projects, and activities. Similarly, no significant difference was found in the level of commitment to the area projects. However, there was a significant difference in the level of commitment of Supreme Pupil Government Officers when grouped and compared according to the type of school in the area, its programs, and its activities. The study results call for SPG officers, advisers, school heads, teachers, and pupils to collaborate, conduct period orientations on their duties and responsibilities, and enhance the leadership skills of SPG Officers.

Keywords: Extra-curricular activities, Supreme Pupil Government Officers, participation and commitment, Negros Occidental, Philippines

Introduction:

Nature of the Problem

The Supreme Pupil Government (SPG) holds a significant role in Philippine elementary schools, serving as the primary extracurricular student organization. Its establishment, guided by the directives of the Department of Education, reflects its importance in promoting student welfare and engagement. The SPG will uphold the Department of Education's mission, which is to protect and promote every Filipino's right to a high-quality, equitable, culture-based, and comprehensive basic education where students learn in a child-friendly, gender-sensitive, safe, and motivating environment, as stated in Article III, Section 2, of its Constitution and By-laws (DepEd Order 47, s. 2014).

One aspect of students' holistic development that has been neglected since schools were closed because of COVID-19 is student leadership (Bantugan et al., 2021). This crisis brought about a great deal of obstacles and changes in education that affected parents, students, teachers, and the school as a whole. It also hinders the continuation of the implementation of many projects, programs, and activities in the school and has an impact on the provision of high-quality basic education in the Philippines.

Current State of Knowledge

Rosch and Collins (2018) found that participation in student organizations provided an environment for the development of students' leadership capacities. In this case, he found that most of these organizations were created to pursue community-based or campus-based impact. The experiences of young leaders in the school educate and inform them of greater opportunities to be involved and take part in school governance. He also added that experiences taught pupil-leaders to handle authority, gain personal identity, and grab opportunities (Lara et al., 2019).

It is claimed that leaders are an organization's heart and soul. These days, educators are molding and training students to be adaptable and flexible in the face of adversity. In addition to encouraging students' responses, this is a preparation for their future societal roles. This generation's youth will assume responsibility for the nation's continued development and advancement (Lualhati, 2019).

Arribado (2018) states that successful school activities and development require leadership committed to advancing the student body's interests and upholding and adhering to the Department of Education's (DepEd) Mission Statement. The student leaders must be evaluated with the clear intention of improvement and development if they are to carry out their roles as essential members of the student government program to the fullest extent possible.

Theoretical Underpinnings

This paper is anchored on Alexander Astin's Theory of Involvement, which asserts that a student must be actively involved on campus for learning and growth to occur to the fullest. The amount of learning and personal growth that a student receives is directly impacted by the nature and volume of their activity on campus. According to Alexander Astin's 1985 theory of student involvement, schools should consider how their desired outcomes relate to the way that students grow and evolve as a result of participating in extracurricular activities. Additionally, it explains how students age, progress, and improve their social abilities throughout their whole time in school. Their engagement in school-related programs, projects, and activities is necessary for this development.

The researcher also used Robert K. Greenleaf's Servant Theory as a foundation for the Commitment of the Supreme Pupil Government. According to the philosophy of servant leadership, an individual can only be an effective leader once they are willing to serve others (Greenleaf, 1977). Servant leaders prioritize working in teams and motivating others around them. They are primarily concerned with the needs of their followers or employees since a thriving community will benefit the organization where they operate.

Objectives of the Study

This study aimed to determine the level of participation and commitment of Supreme Pupil Government Officers to school programs, projects, and activities in a first-class, highly urbanized city in Western Visayas, Philippines, during the School Year 2022-2023. Specifically, this study sought to determine (1) the level of participation of Supreme Pupil Government Officers, (2) the level of commitment of Supreme Pupil Government Officers, (3) the significant difference in the level of Participation of Supreme Pupil Government Officers when grouped and compared according to the sex, grade level, and type of School (4) the significant difference in the level of commitment of Supreme Pupil Government Officers when grouped according to the same variables.

Research Methodology:

This section presents the methodology of the study. It discusses the research design, locale of the study, subject and the participants, the data gathering procedure, which includes the research instrument and the test of its validity and reliability, the data-processing procedure, the analytical schemes, and the statistical tools.

Research Design

In this study, the researcher utilized the descriptive-quantitative research design to determine the level of participation and commitment of Supreme Pupil Government Officers in a medium-sized school division in Central Philippines for the School Year 2022-2023. The researcher considered this design as the most appropriate because it involved the description of the Supreme Pupil Government in terms of their participation and commitment to programs, projects, and activities.

Respondents

The respondents of the study were the 100 Supreme Pupil Government Officers from one (1) of the seven (7) established Districts in a first-class, highly urbanized city in Western Visayas, Philippines, for the School Year 2022-2023, using purposive sampling.

Instrument

The instrument used for this study was a 45-item self-made questionnaire, which was divided into two main sections. Section I was composed of the respondents' profiles, such as sex, grade level, and type of school. Section II determines the level of participation and commitment of the Supreme Pupil Government Officers in schools, which consists of areas such as programs, projects, and activities. Each item was rated on a scale of 1

to 5, using a 5-point Likert scale rating with 5 as very high, 4 as high, 3 as moderate, 2 as low, and 1 as very low.

Procedures

Data Collection

To ensure the smoother conduct of the study, the researcher sought permission from the School Division Superintendent to undertake the study. Upon approval, the researcher set a schedule for the data gathering with a letter of request to the District's School Principals. The researcher administered and retrieved the research instrument to ensure 100% retrieval. After the conduct, questionnaires were retrieved, and the data was tallied, tabulated, analyzed, and interpreted according to the specific problem and hypotheses set forth in this study.

Data Analysis/Statistical Treatment

This study utilized various analytical approaches consistent with the study's research objectives. Objectives 1-2 used the descriptive analytical scheme and mean as statistical tools to determine the level of participation and commitment of Supreme Pupil Government Officers. Objectives 3-4 used the comparative analytical scheme, Mann-Whitney U-Test, and Kruskal Wallis H-Test to determine whether a significant difference exists in the level of participation and commitment of Supreme Pupil Government Officers when grouped according to sex, grade level, and type of school.

Ethical Considerations

This research paper strived to minimize the risk of harm to its target respondents by assuring them of the confidentiality of their responses and ensuring their anonymity throughout the entire research process. At the onset, this researcher secured their free, prior informed consent and assured them of their right to withdraw from their research participation if deemed necessary. No personal data compromising the respondents' identity were collected in adherence to the Data Privacy Act of 2012, specifically on accessing the data both by the researcher and the analyst. The respondents were assured that no information that discloses their identity will be released or published without their consent, except when extremely necessary. All collected materials were appropriately disposed of by machine shredding or dissolved in water after the submission of the study. At the same time, soft copies of the data were deleted, leaving no chance of future retrieval.

Results and Discussion

This section deals with the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of data gathered to carry out the objectives of this study.

Level of Participation of Supreme Pupil Government Officers according to Programs, Projects, and Activities

Table 1

Level of Participation of Supreme Pupil Government Officers in the School Programs

Area	Mean	Interpretation
A. Program <i>I participated in...</i>		
1. national greening program and other environment-related activities to provide a good environment for learning.	4.40	Very High Level
2. school reading program and other tutorial services.	4.57	Very High Level
3. core values (Maka-Diyos, Maka-tao, Makakalikasan at Makabansa) advocacy program	4.64	Very High Level
4. ensuring that the school is a smoke/tobacco-free place.	4.56	Very High Level
5. awareness campaign program to encourage parents to enlist their five-year-old children for kindergarten.	4.46	Very High Level
Overall Mean	4.53	Very High Level

Table 1 shows the Supreme Pupil Government's participation level according to programs with an overall mean score of 4.53, interpreted as "Very high level."

Item No. 3 obtained the highest mean score of 4.64, which states "core values (Maka-Diyos, Maka-*tao*, Makakalikasan at Makabansa) advocacy program" interpreted as "very high level," while Item No. 1 got the lowest mean score of 4.40 which states "national greening program and other environment-related activities to provide a good environment for learning" interpreted as "very high level."

This means that Supreme Pupil Government Officers participated in the organization's mandated school programs, such as core values (Maka-Diyos, Maka-*tao*, Makakalikasan at Makabansa) advocacy program. It shows that they have exemplary performance in achieving the goals and objectives through applying their significant roles and functions in their respective school. Their participation, particularly their responsibilities and contributions, were essential to the accomplishments of every academic institution.

However, SPG Officers may need help participating in the National Greening Program, which can be attributed to factors such as a lack of resources and motivation.

The above findings reaffirm the Constitution and By-Laws of the Supreme Pupil Government (SPG) that the SPG as a student organization is institutionalized to implement pertinent programs, projects, and activities in Philippine schools as mandated by the Department of Education. Likewise, it should also adhere to the core values of the Department of Education, which are Maka-Diyos, Maka-*tao*, Maka-kalikasan, and Makabansa.

Table 2
Level of Participation of Supreme Pupil Government Officers in School Projects

Area	Mean	Interpretation
B. Projects <i>I participated in...</i>		
1. conducting book and toy drive and other school supplies for donation to schools.	4.45	Very High Level
2. the proper implementation of Zero Waste Management in the school through the use of the 3Rs Project (Reduce, Re-use, Recycle).	4.58	Very High Level
3. tree planting project in the school and the community.	4.50	Very High Level
4. The school recycling project will provide pupils with hands-on experience and help them take responsibility for keeping the environment clean.	4.55	Very High Level
5. peer coaching services/projects to promote quality education and academic excellence.	4.55	Very High Level
Overall Mean	4.53	Very High Level

Table 2 shows the level of participation of the Supreme Pupil Government according to the area projects. The overall mean score is 4.53, interpreted as "Very High Level."

Item No. 2 obtained the highest mean score of 4.58, which states "the proper implementation of the Zero Waste Management in the school through the use of 3Rs Project (Reduce, Re-use, Recycle)" interpreted as "very high level." In contrast, Item No. 1 got the lowest mean score of 4.45, which states that "conducting book and toy drive and other school supplies for donation to schools is interpreted as a "very high level."

This implies that Supreme Pupil Government Officers participated in the Department of Education's mandated projects, such as the proper implementation of Zero Waste Management in the school through the use of the 3Rs Project (Reduce, Re-use, Recycle) and school recycling project to provide pupils with hands-on experience and to take responsibility for keeping the environment clean. It only shows that SPG Officers also focused on the School Organization's projects promoting a clean and green environment, which benefited the pupils and the whole school community.

This was confirmed by Rosch and Collins (2018), who believed that participation in student organizations provided an environment for the development of students' leadership capacities. In this case, he found that most of these organizations were created to pursue community-based or campus-based impact.

Table 3
Level of Participation of Supreme Pupil Government Officers in School Activities

Area	Mean	Interpretation
C. Activities <i>I participated in...</i>		
1. enforcing policies designed to protect and promote the students' rights and welfare.	4.46	Very High Level
2. organizing the participation of students and volunteers in the annual Brigada Eskwela.	4.60	Very High Level
3. honoring teachers by providing quality education at all levels during the teacher's month/ teacher's day.	4.72	Very High Level
4. leadership training/formation to enhance leadership skills.	4.77	Very High Level
5. Students led school watching and hazard mapping to identify potential hazards and risks within and around the schools.	4.50	Very High Level
Overall Mean	4.61	Very High Level

Table 3 shows the level of participation of the Supreme Pupil Government according to the area activities. The overall mean score is 4.61, interpreted as "Very high level."

Item No. 4 obtained the highest mean score of 4.77, which states "leadership training/formation to enhance leadership skills" interpreted as "very high level." In contrast, Item No. 1 got the lowest mean score of 4.46, which states that "enforcing policies designed to protect and promote the students' rights and welfare" is interpreted as a "very high level."

This signifies that Supreme Pupil Government Officers participated in the organization's activities like leadership training/formation to enhance leadership skills. Participating in this activity helps Supreme Pupil Government Officers meet their needs in order to carry out their duties and responsibilities successfully. On the other hand, SPG officers have difficulties participating in and organizing activities that foster the rights and welfare of the students. This could be due to a need for more guidance from the SPG adviser.

Adams et al. (2018) assert that student leaders should be exposed to leadership development programs that enable them to have increased "knowledge, competence, skills, and capabilities as leaders. It was also found that leadership training is very important for developing the leadership abilities of student leaders. There are several studies that examined the importance of Leadership Training.

Level of Commitment of Supreme Pupil Government Officers to Programs, Projects, and Activities

Table 4

Level of Commitment of Supreme Pupil Government Officers in School Programs

Area	Mean	Interpretation
A. Program <i>I committed to...</i>		
1. national greening program and other environment-related activities to provide a good environment for learning.	4.46	Very High Level
2. school reading program and other tutorial services.	4.48	Very High Level
3. core values (Maka-Diyos, Maka-tao, Makakalikasan at Makabansa) advocacy program.	4.66	Very High Level
4. ensuring that the school is a smoke/tobacco-free place.	4.43	Very High Level
5. awareness campaign program to encourage parents to enlist their five-year-old children for kindergarten.	4.60	Very High Level
Overall Mean	4.53	Very High Level

Table 4 presents the commitment of the Supreme Pupil Government Officers according to the area programs. The overall mean score is 4.53, interpreted as "Very high level."

Item No. 3 obtained the highest mean score of 4.66, which states that "core values (Maka-Diyos, Maka-tao, Makakalikasan at Makabansa) advocacy program" interpreted as "very high level." At the same time, Item No. 3 got the lowest mean score of 4.43, which states "ensuring that the school is a smoke/tobacco-free place" interpreted as "very high level."

This result indicates that Supreme Pupil Government Officers are committed to fostering and safeguarding the mandated programs of the Department of Education that focus on implementing the core values (Maka-Diyos, Maka-tao, Makakalikasan at Makabansa). This is to inspire and develop students' passionate love for God, love for fellowmen, love for nature, and love for the country. They focus on the holistic development of the pupils.

This result was affirmed by the Dep Ed Order No. 47, series of 2014, otherwise known as the Constitution and By-Laws of the Supreme Pupil Government in Elementary School. It was constitutionalized to help students develop a passionate love of the country, values, and competencies that will enable them to realize their full potential and to contribute meaningfully to the nation.

Table 5
Level of Commitment of Supreme Pupil Government Officers in School Projects

Area	Mean	Interpretation
B. Projects		
<i>I committed to...</i>		
1. conducting book and toy drive and other school supplies for donation to schools.	4.42	Very High Level
2. the proper implementation of Zero Waste Management in the school through the use of the 3Rs Project (Reduce, Re-use, Recycle).	4.52	Very High Level
3. tree planting project in the school and in the community.	4.49	Very High Level
4. The school recycling project will provide pupils with hands-on experience and help them take responsibility for keeping the environment clean.	4.66	Very High Level
5. peer coaching services/projects to promote quality education and academic excellence.	4.38	Very High Level
Overall Mean	4.49	Very High Level

Table 5 presents the level of commitment of the Supreme Pupil Government according to the area projects. The overall mean score is 4.49, interpreted as "Very high level."

Item No. 4 obtained the highest mean score of 4.66, which states, "school recycling project to provide pupils with hands-on experience and to take responsibility for keeping the environment clean," interpreted as "very high level." At the same time, Item No. 5 got the lowest mean score of 4.40, which states that "peer coaching services/projects to promote quality education and academic excellence" is interpreted as a "very high level."

This implies that most of the Supreme Pupil Government Officers devote themselves to implementing the mandated projects in their respective schools, like the school recycling project, to provide pupils with hands-on experience and take responsibility for keeping the environment clean. These projects also foster meaningful relationships between officers and their peers and positively impact their social skills, academic achievement, and leadership abilities. In addition, this project will strengthen the integration of environmental concerns into school curricula.

The slightly lower score on item 5 suggests that SPG officers may need help managing their time between academics and extra-curricular activities.

Article III, Declaration of Principles, Objectives, and Policies in the Constitution and By-Laws, states that the SPG shall be committed to putting the values, principles, and ideals of SPG into action through academics,

socio-civic, leadership programs, and activities. It is a policy to serve with utmost responsibility, integrity, loyalty, efficiency, and professionalism.

Table 6
Level of Commitment of Supreme Pupil Government Officers in School Activities

Area	Mean	Interpretation
C. Activities <i>I committed to...</i>		
1. enforcing policies designed to protect and promote the students' rights and welfare.	4.37	Very High Level
2. organizing the participation of students and volunteers in the annual Brigada Eskwela.	4.49	Very High Level
3. honoring teachers by providing quality education at all levels during the teacher's month/ teacher's day.	4.73	Very High Level
4. leadership training/formation to enhance leadership skills.	4.64	Very High Level
5. Students led school watching and hazard mapping to identify potential hazards and risks within and around the schools.	4.54	Very High Level
Overall Mean	4.55	Very High Level

Table 6 shows the level of commitment of the Supreme Pupil Government according to the area activities. The overall mean score is 4.55, interpreted as "Very high level."

Item No. 3 obtained the highest mean score of 4.73, which states "honoring teachers in providing quality education at all levels during the teacher's Month/ teacher's day," interpreted as "very high level," while Item No. 1 got the lowest mean score of 4.37 which states "enforcing policies designed to protect and promote the students' rights and welfare" interpreted as "very high level."

The result signifies that Supreme Pupil Government Officers gave their time and effort to different activities of the organization, especially in honoring teachers by providing quality education at all levels during the teacher's month/ teacher's day. It only means that they highlighted the importance of teachers in ensuring that all children and young people can exercise their right to quality education. Moreover, the Teacher's Day Celebration is in pursuance of the Presidential Proclamation and Republic Act No. 10743, declaring the fifth day of October of every year a National Teacher's Day.

According to Marchione (2022), a sufficient balance of leadership, school, personal time, and work may differ for everyone, but finding the appropriate time allocation for each commitment can clearly influence an individual's life. It is also important that personal time is a crucial component for student leadership success because oftentimes, it may not be implemented at all. From leadership, there can be a variety of feelings that derive from the abundance of acquired activities, but finding that personal stability could mitigate or altogether remove the potential negative impacts.

Comparative Analysis in the Level of Participation of Supreme Pupil Government Officers according to School Programs, Projects, and Activities when Grouped by Sex, Grade Level, and Type of School

Table 7
Difference in the Level of Participation of Supreme Pupil Government Officers in School Programs when Grouped according to the Aforementioned Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Kruskal Wallis H	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Sex	Male	26	51.54	2.603	935.000	0.828	0.05	Not Significant
	Female	74	50.14					
Grade Level	Grade 4	18	60.06	3.372		0.272	0.05	Not Significant
	Grade 5	33	49.62					
Type of School	Grade 6	49	47.58			0.185		Not Significant
	Medium	39	46.78					
	Large	13	42.38					

Mega 48 55.72

Table 7 shows the difference in the level of participation of Supreme Pupil Government Officers according to the area programs when grouped and compared according to sex, grade level, and type of school.

The computed Mann-Whitney U-Test, Kruskal Wallis, and *p*-value showed no significant differences when respondents were grouped according to sex (935.000, 0.828); grade level (2.603, 0.272); and type of school (3.372, 0.185) where all the calculated *p*-values were higher than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, no significant differences were found. Therefore, the hypothesis that states "there is no significant difference in the level of participation of Supreme Pupil Government Officers according to the area programs when grouped and compared according to sex, grade level and type of school" was "accepted."

This result indicates that the level of participation of Supreme Pupil Government Officers in the area program is not influenced by their sex, grade level, and type of school.

Furthermore, this result indicates that the SPG officers, despite some difficulties encountered, still fulfill their responsibilities and duties as stated in the SPG Constitution and By-Laws.

Table 8
Difference in the Level of Participation of Supreme Pupil Government Officers in School Projects when Grouped according to the Aforementioned Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Kruskal Wallis H	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Sex	Male	26	55.56	2.285	830.500	0.289	0.05	Not Significant
	Female	74	48.72					
Grade Level	Grade 4	18	56.81	0.613		0.736	0.05	Not Significant
	Grade 5	33	53.27					
	Grade 6	49	46.32					
Type of School	Medium	39	48.31					Not Significant
	Large	13	55.23					
	Mega	48	51.00					

Table 8 depicts the difference in the level of participation of Supreme Pupil Government Officers according to the area project when grouped and compared according to sex, grade level, and type of school.

The computed Mann-Whitney U-Test, Kruskal Wallis, and *p*-value showed no significant differences when respondents were grouped according to sex (830.500, 0.289); grade level (2.285, 0.319); and type of school (0.613, 0.736) where all the calculated *p*-values were higher than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, no significant differences were found. Therefore, the hypothesis that states "there is no significant difference in the level of participation of Supreme Pupil Government Officers according to the area projects when grouped and compared according to sex, grade level and type of school" was "accepted."

The result of the study implies that irrespective of sex, grade level, and type of school of the Supreme Pupil Government Officers, their level of participation in the area projects remains high.

Leaders are said to be the heart and soul of any organization. Students nowadays are being shaped and trained to be flexible and adaptive in meeting the challenges of life. This is not only to promote responsiveness among students but, most importantly, to prepare them for their future roles in society. The youth of this generation will take the obligation of ensuring the country's further development and progress (Lualhati, 2019).

Table 9
Difference in the Level of Participation of Supreme Pupil Government Officers in School Activities when Grouped according to the Aforementioned Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Kruskal Wallis H	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Sex	Male	26	47.98	0.925	896.500	0.598	0.05	Not Significant
	Female	74	51.39					
Grade Level	Grade 4	18	53.47			0.630		Not Significant
	Grade 5	33	53.00					

	Grade 6	49	47.72			
	Medium	39	58.09			
Type of School	Large	13	50.69	5.109	0.078	Not Significant
	Mega	48	44.28			

Table 9 indicates the difference in the level of participation of Supreme Pupil Government Officers according to the area activities when grouped and compared according to sex, grade level, and type of school.

When grouped according to all variables of sex, grade level, and type of school, all the computed *p*-values, which range from 0.078 to 0.630, were higher than the 0.05 level of significance, which is interpreted as "not significant."

Therefore, the hypothesis that states "there is no significant difference in the level of participation of Supreme Pupil Government Officers according to the area activities when grouped and compared according to sex, grade level and type of school" was "accepted."

The result of the study indicates that irrespective of the sex, grade level, and type of school of the respondents, their participation in school activities remains high. As revealed by the study, despite some challenges, Supreme Pupil Government Officers did their best to participate in and implement activities promoting students' holistic development.

This is the true quality of a good leader; despite the circumstances, they continue to serve their fellow students.

Gregorio (2019) discussed that the Supreme Pupil Government impacts social skills. It also takes advantage of participation in the school organization system. Participation in school organizations and activities might influence young people's mental well-being by reducing stress, staying fit, and feeling better about their appearance.

Comparative Analysis in the Level of Commitment of Supreme Pupil Government Officers according to School Programs, Projects, and Activities when Grouped by Sex, Grade Level, and Type of School

Table 10

Difference in the Level of Commitment of Supreme Pupil Government Officers in School Programs when Grouped according to the Aforementioned Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Kruskal Wallis H	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Sex	Male	26	44.06		794.500	0.181	0.05	Not Significant
	Female	74	52.76					
Grade Level	Grade 4	18	57.64	1.494		0.474	0.05	Not Significant
	Grade 5	33	50.27					
	Grade 6	49	48.03					
Type of School	Medium	39	60.06	7.594		0.022		Significant
	Large	13	39.85					
	Mega	48	45.61					

Table 10 indicates the difference in the level of commitment of Supreme Pupil Government Officers according to the area programs when grouped and compared according to sex, grade level, and type of school.

As computed statistically, the Mann-Whitney U-Test and *p*-values, when grouped according to the variable of sex, were 7954.500 and 0.181, respectively, and for the grade level, the Kruskal Wallis H and *p*-values were 1.494 and 0.474, where all the calculated *p*-values were higher than the 0.05 level of significance.

This means that the hypothesis that states "there is no significant difference in the level of commitment of Supreme Pupil Government Officers according to the area programs when grouped and compared according to sex and grade level was therefore "accepted."

This result indicates that the Supreme Pupil Government Officers have a consistent view of their commitment to the organization's mandated programs across all groupings. As revealed by the study, despite some difficulties encountered, the commitment of the SPG officer was high.

However, when grouped according to the type of school, the computed p -values (0.022) registered a figure lower than the 0.05 level of significance, interpreted as "significant." This means that the hypothesis that states "there is no significant difference in the level of commitment of Supreme Pupil Government Officers according to the area programs when grouped and compared according to the type of school was therefore "rejected."

This indicates that there are differences in the perception of the respondents from medium, large, and mega schools when evaluating their own commitment to the area programs. This could be attributed to the size of the school and the number of pupils. Smaller schools can easily be monitored by their SPG adviser and school head.

According to Rollon (2023), the school sustains the concepts of organization structures and functions of SPG Commitment in order to uphold the union of SPG Organization. The school also sustains and innovates activities that allow all pupils to join any organization regardless of academic and extra-curricular activities.

Table 11
Difference in the Level of Commitment of Supreme Pupil Government Officers in School Projects when Grouped according to the Aforementioned Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Kruskal Wallis H	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Sex	Male	26	51.71	3.205	930.500	0.800	0.05	Not Significant
	Female	74	50.07					
Grade Level	Grade 4	18	61.22	1.830		0.401	0.05	Not Significant
	Grade 5	33	49.18					
	Grade 6	49	47.45					
Type of School	Medium	39	54.31					Not Significant
	Large	13	42.31					
	Mega	48	49.63					

Table 11 reveals the difference in the level of commitment of Supreme Pupil Government Officers according to the area projects when grouped and compared according to sex, grade level, and type of school.

Accordingly, when grouped according to sex, the computed Mann-Whitney U test was 930.500, and the p -value was 0.800, which is higher than the 0.05 level of significance, interpreted as "not significant."

Moreover, when grouped according to grade level and type of school, the computed Kruskal Wallis H were 3.205 and 1.830, and the p -values were 0.201 and 0.401, which were higher than the 0.05 level of significance, likewise, interpreted as "not significant."

Thus, the hypothesis that states "there is no significant difference in the level of level of commitment of Supreme Pupil Government Officers according to the area projects when grouped and compared according to sex, grade level and type of school" was therefore "accepted."

This implies that the Supreme Pupil Government's commitment to projects is indeed high, regardless of sex, grade level, and type of school. Giving the SPG officers a variety of opportunities to develop their leadership knowledge, abilities, and attitudes creates the foundation for excellent governance.

According to Aviles (2021), students' involvement in charitable activities offers them many benefits and satisfaction while helping other youths in the community.

Table 12
Difference in the Level of Commitment of Supreme Pupil Government Officers in School Activities when Grouped according to the Aforementioned Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Kruskal Wallis H	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Sex	Male	26	43.00	1.211	767.000	0.119	0.05	Not Significant
	Female	74	53.14					
Grade Level	Grade 4	18	48.39			0.546		Not Significant
	Grade 5	33	46.95					
	Grade 6	49	53.66					

Type of School	Medium	39	60.73			
	Large	13	42.85	8.247	0.016	Significant
	Mega	48	44.26			

Table 12 depicts the difference in the level of commitment of Supreme Pupil Government Officers according to the area activities when grouped and compared according to sex, grade level, and type of school.

The computed Mann-Whitney U-Test, Kruskal Wallis H, and p -value showed no significant differences when respondents were grouped according to sex (767.000, 0.119) and grade level (1.211, 0.546), where all the calculated p -values were higher than the 0.05 level of significance.

Thus, no significant differences were found. Therefore, the hypothesis that states "there is no significant difference in the level of commitment of Supreme Pupil Government Officers according to the area activities when grouped and compared according to sex and grade level was "accepted."

This finding shows that Supreme Pupil Government Officers have a consistent perception of their commitment to the organization's activities. The survey showed that despite various challenges faced, SPG officers' commitment was evident.

However, when grouped according to the type of school, the computed p -values (0.016) registered a figure lower than the 0.05 level of significance, interpreted as "significant." This means that the hypothesis that states "there is no significant difference in the level of commitment of Supreme Pupil Government Officers according to the area activities when grouped and compared according to the type of school was therefore "rejected."

This result showed differences in the respondents' perception of medium, large, and mega schools in assessing their own commitment to the area activities. This could be attributed to the size of the school and the number of pupils. Due to the lesser number of pupils and smaller type of school, the SPG officers and its organization can focus and perform their roles and functions effectively.

Pascua and Dulos (2020) believed that leaders should be more open to the undertakings of the organization to address problems and issues. Excellent training design should be used to address issues, concerns, and problems of the organization.

Conclusions

The participation and commitment among Supreme Pupil Government Officers typically signify several positive aspects within the student organization, like their dedication and intrinsic motivation in their mandated duties. They collaborate effectively with each other, school administrators, teachers, and other stakeholders. They work together cohesively to address student concerns, plan and implement projects, and achieve common goals. Moreover, they demonstrate dedication and initiative in fulfilling their roles and responsibilities, effectively leading their peers, and promoting positive change within the school community. A vibrant, proactive, and inclusive pupil organization that actively engages with the student body, fosters leadership development, and collaborates to bring about positive change within the school community is indicated by the Supreme Pupil Government's overall high participation and commitment. Lastly, their commitment to serving their peers and the school community drives the success and effectiveness of the student government's initiatives and activities.

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